

Zooplankton Diversity and Population Density in the Ecological Lake of Samaspur Bird Sanctuary

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Abstract

The present study was conducted to deals with population density and diversity at ecological Lake of Samaspur birds Sanctuary. Samples were collected on a monthly basis. The samples were evaluated quantitatively and the Zooplankton identified from collected samples. Qualitative and quantitative analysis of Zooplankton population density indicates the dominance of some species during whole investigation period (2021-2022). The five major group of Zooplankton observed so far, are Rotifera, Cladocera Copepoda, Protozoan and ostracods. The study shows that population density found higher during summer season.

Keywords Zooplankton, Lake of Samaspur Bird Sanctuary.

Introduction

The key role of fresh water Zooplankton is to transfer energy from one tropic level to other in the aquatic habitat. Besides, they are also used as biological indicators of tropic status of water body. Zooplanktons are primary food for fishes and can be used as indicators of tropic status of water body. Their location in distribution and abundance can be used to estimate the fishery potential of a water body. Hutchinson. G. E (1967) (Pennak 1953).

Objective of study

The present study was conducted to deals with population density and diversity at ecological Lake of Samaspur birds Sanctuary.

Review of Literature

The knowledge of their abundance, species diversity and special distribution is important in understanding trophodynamic and tropic progression of water bodies (S. M. Pawar and V. B. Supugade, 2017). Phytoplankton and Zooplankton undertake a journey from bottom to surface at the approach of darkness. Light intensity is considered the main factor, in addition to other factors like temperature, pressure, gravity and preadtors to influence this phenomenon. (Sreelatha, K.and Rajalakshmi. S. 2005).To understanding their role in the ecosystem many attempts has been made in the past few years (Micheal, 1980). The present study deals with zooplankton diversity & density of fresh water body at birds sanctuary lake in Samaspur

Methodology

Ecological Samaspur birds Sanctuary Lake is situated near Salon in Raebareli district, Uttar Pradesh ([25°59'45"N 81°23'30"E](#)). It is famous for migratory birds. More than 250 varieties of birds can be seen there, some of which travel more than 5000 km to get there. Lake has a wide area Approx. 2600 Sqm. Rich vegetation is present at the bottom of lake. From the lake water samples were collected for analysis of physio-chemical parameters, diversity and density of zooplanktons. The study was conducted for a period of January 2021 to December 2022. Zooplankton density was determined by sieving 25 litres of the lake surface water from the selected site using plankton net, mesh size 40

micron and 5% formaldehyde is used to preserve the sample for further studies in laboratory. For quantitative analysis one drop of water was taken with the help of ordinary dropper on Sedgwick Rafter, examined under microscope to study the qualitative and quantitative analysis of plankton (Weltch 1948)¹³.

Result and Discussion

The list of population density of zooplankton species in the ecological lake of Samaspur birds Sanctuary.

Cladocera:

1. Daphnia magna
2. Daphnia sp.
3. Chydorus sphaericus
4. Wlssicsia ienistinesis

Rotifera:

1. Platyias patulus
2. Asplanchna sp.
3. Lecane
4. Keratella

Protozoa

1. Amoeba proteus
2. Radiolaria
3. Paramecium
4. Ciliates

Copepoda :

1. Calanodia
2. Cyclops sp.
3. Diaptomus napalus
4. Nauplius sp.

Rotifera was found dominant species among all other species due to favourable chemical condition in the lake. Water pH and temperature were also the main factors in the abundance of different rotifer sp. (Yousuf and Quadari, 1981)¹⁴, (Gulati, 1978)⁵ suggested that, if the food supply is high or increasing for a certain period of time than the Cladoceran usually buildup more in number and dominate the lake zooplankton. Population of Cladoceran and Protozoa multiply rapidly when food is available in plenty. These effects show the high eutrophication in the lake. Some group of Ciliophora also show the organic pollution in lake water. Study shows that zooplankton population density was maximum in summer season (Table- 3). The high density in summer season may be correlated to higher temperature and favourable environment conditions. ((Tripathi and Adhikari 1990)⁹ considered water temperature as the most important controlling factor for the abundance of zooplankton. In present study high population density in summer season found direct relationship with phytoplankton and increased organic waste

Table 1: Density variation of zooplankton (unit/lit.) on monthly basis at Ecological lake of Samaspur birds Sanctuary.

2021					
Month	Rotifera	Cladocera	Protozoa	Copepoda	Average
Jan	16168.5	687.4	10265.0	9878.0	9249.7
Feb	16465.0	895.3	12081.3	10523.0	9991.2
March	18650.0	1098.0	11229.0	13658.3	11158.8
April	18425.0	1165.2	13729.0	15428.0	12186.8
May	18498.4	1236.0	14389.0	13425	11887.1
June	21629.8	1729.4	16597.5	18265.2	14555.5
July	18425.0	625.0	13246.3	7225.0	9880.3
Aug.	9925.3	542.0	6425.3	4629.0	5380.4
Sept.	10111.4	512.3	6928.0	6413.0	5991.2
Oct.	11365.0	604.3	9118.0	8941.5	7502.2
Nov.	14056.0	703.0	9956.3	9123.3	8459.7
Dec.	15089.3	745.0	10465.4	8614.0	8728.4

Table 2: Density variation of zooplankton (unit/lit.) on monthly basis at Ecological lake of Samaspur birds Sanctuary.

2022					
Month	Rotifera	Cladocera	Protozoa	Copepoda	Average
Jan	15887.0	704.0	10567.0	9708.0	9216.5
Feb	16265.5	855.2	12288.0	11523.2	10232.9
March	18358.0	998.0	12829.4	12058.0	11060.9
April	18425.0	1162.2	13929.5	13228.0	11686.2
May	18698.2	1296.0	14589.0	14725.4	12327.2
June	21892.3	1529.6	15897.4	18665.3	14496.2
July	18338.0	822.0	15246.3	7525.0	10482.8
Aug.	9125.2	642.0	6325.6	3729.4	4955.6
Sept.	9868.3	698.4	6828.3	4813.0	5552
Oct.	11375.0	714.3	8818.0	5941.0	6712.1
Nov.	13058.0	789.0	9946.0	6623.6	7604.2
Dec.	13489.5	815.0	10165.5	7114.0	7896

Table 3: Seasonal variations of total zooplanktons at Ecological lake of Samaspur birds Sanctuary.

2001			2022		
Summer	Monsoon	Winter	Summer	Monsoon	Winter
12447	7188	8982	12392	6925	8737

Table 4: % Population of zooplanktons diversity at Ecological lake of Samaspur birds Sanctuary in 2022.

Season	Rotifera	Cladocera	Protozoa	Copepoda
Summer	39.02%	2.51%	28.87%	29.59%
Monsoon	43.95%	2.59%	33.58%	19.86%
Winter	41.98%	2.26%	30.73%	25.01%

Figure-1 Zooplankton diversity at Ecological lake of Samaspur birds Sanctuary in 2022.

Conclusion

The conclusion of this study is that Rotifers are dominant group among Cladocera, Protozoa and Copepoda during all seasons. Population density is seen maximum in summer season and minimum in Monsoon season. It has been seen that the quality and quantity of zooplankton fluctuated monthly and seasonally in the ecological lake of Samaspur birds Sanctuary.

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